

Successful Public Management, Factors that Improve it

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on an analysis of factors focused on the analysis of the needs of public entities of the three levels of government in the provision of public services demanded by citizens. Through the analysis of current Public Management (PM), it is intended to establish proposals for improvement through Organizational Development (OD), in the field of public services; to generate with this concepts focused on the application of this OD in mainly public activities, to merge the benefits of the principle of efficiency towards the public, generating an Efficient Public Management (EPM) also supported by principles of economy and effectiveness, which are linked to the efficiency converge in a successful management of resources focused on the achievement of objectives and satisfaction of social needs.

KEYWORDS: Public Organizational Development (POD), Efficient Public Management (EPM), Organizational Change, Governance

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I. INTRODUCTION

The dynamics of Public Management (PM) and its close interaction in daily life with citizens indicates that it is the pressure of the latter that guides public entities to make permanent changes in the processes that are carried out for the provision of goods and services.

The greater the number of users of public services, the greater the pressure to achieve an efficient and effective process in meeting the demands and needs of citizens.

The greater the number of public Servants involved in the provision of a public service, the greater the complexity in the organization of production processes.

As Public Administration, the municipalities, the States and the Central Government itself face a series of problems in their structure and operation, as happens to other types of organizations, be they private, social or public. These three orders of government face structural problems that also affect the functional aspect of the organizations, so this must be complemented with a performance that turns them into efficient entities, with the capacity to respond to the current social welfare needs of their population. It demands him.

It is for this reason that the application of an Organizational Development (OD) program in the Public Management is, without a doubt, an alternative to improve its performance and favor its modernization, which will be successful if considered for the characteristics of each public entity. It should not be forgotten that these are public organizations, of a different nature from the private ones, in addition to the fact that in Mexico there is a very marked regional heterogeneity, and these aspects must be taken into account when considering the application of an OD program.

If we were to apply OD in a municipality, for example, as has been done in the private sector, we will be falling into a very recurrent error that would lead to failure in the intention that this tool can improve local performance.

Discussions on public policy and administration have focused on another issue: the administrative capacity of States. In other words, now, beyond analyzing the configuration of government regimes and the division of power, the objective has been to answer how to ensure that the government apparatus, within a framework of legality, generates results, delivers quality services and complies with citizen expectations, OLACEFS [18].

II. BACKGROUND

A. Citizenship and Efficient Public Management (EPM)

Through the analysis of current Public Management (PM), it is intended to establish proposals for improvement through Organizational Development, in the field of public services in general.

To achieve the strengthening of the PM, a redistribution of functions and powers is necessary, that is, a modification of intergovernmental relations, promoting the culture of shared, intercommunicated, responsible and coordinated management, converting the criteria of autonomy and sovereignty of the City Council, in others of political autonomy circumscribed to the conduct of their lines of action and strategies of internal government.

Therefore, the importance of a good PM lies in being aware of the need to be closer to the population; the municipal entity is the first provider of public services and the one where social processes initially converge. Therefore, it is possible to infer that the municipal entities have suffered the most relevant political movements in the history of the Mexican PM and it is until recently that it has been given the importance it has. At least in a normative way it is recognized as a government body, although in practice its autonomy is still violated, for example, in the financial issue, Aguilar Villanueva [1].

III. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A. Efficient and correct Public Management (EPM)

Public Administration and Organizational Development Organizational Development (OD)

It focuses on the concept Organizational change, this presupposes that there is a set of organizational elements whose circumstance is affecting the growth, the development of the same, and particularly of the members of this, and their behaviors and attitudes, towards, the purposes, objectives and organizational goals, Guizar [15].

Cruz Meléndez [11] summarizes that OD is a management tool whose main objective is to promote the planned change to improve performance in administrative, organizational, technological, social and cultural aspects. It arises from the private sector and that is where it has been applied regularly, however, in this work the author proposes that it be used in the Municipal Public Administration, considering certain theoretical considerations.

Why is it that in recent years the study of the government organization has increased?

To successfully carry out the defined programs that emanate from the plans established for the organization, improvement in it is essential.

The various routes that from the "New Public Management" have opened space to travel the study of the public have not spared proposals to approach "the public".

This "new" focus, or field of study of public affairs, allows reviewing, from the organizational aspect, the municipal public sector and helps to feel the usefulness of the application of the OD to obtain the results that are demanded of the municipality in its scope of action and powers, in the first instance and the other orders of government (State and Federal) in the background.

Efficient Public Management (EPM)

The OD has its own aspect of realization, like many of the analysis routes of a new Public Management focused on Efficiency (EPM), which can even be considered as a strategy that focuses on changing beliefs, values, structure, attitudes, abilities and aptitudes of the members of the organizations, so that they can adapt to contextual changes and assume the challenges that this implies, for which the OD must focus its attention on organizational behaviors and focus on the Human Factor, that is It is on this that, it is sought to influence, it is on external and internal elements that affect it that it is intended to work to contribute to raising the effectiveness of the organization in its production processes.

Aguilar Villanueva [1], delves into the principles and tools of the new public management, particularly strategic and quality management, crucial to achieve a competent and effective government. His idea focuses on the fact that the successful management of society is based more on social actors than on the government and requires more resources than those possessed by the government itself.

Public Organizational Development (POD)

The inclusion of the Public in the OD traditionally focused on rather private sectors should basically begin at the municipal level, since it is important to raise basic premises regarding the daily reality of the municipality, Mejía Lira [16].

1. The municipality is a public organization that, beyond its meaning in the structuring of the State, is subject to direct and daily pressure from the citizen in their demands for solutions to their problems and improvement of their quality of life.
2. The variety of services, products or goods that the municipality must provide to the citizen make it the closest governmental link with society.
3. Although the orders of government recognized in the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States (CPEUM) [10] make the municipality the instance with the greatest social proximity, it is also true that it is the one with the greatest vulnerability. However, the most recent reforms carried out to this document and in the local constitutions, the municipality continues to be the governmental piece with the highest degree of sensitivity to the social, cultural, political and economic dynamics of the State structure, municipal autonomy is It is affected by a reduced financial autonomy and by an institutional context that prostrates it at the mercy of the lack of recognition of its "coming of age", both by those who sometimes assume themselves as their parents (the federal or state order), metaphorically speaking, as by those who do not recognize themselves in their tutelary role with all their strengths, in the daily exercise of government responsibility in this area.

Governance

Administration or Public Sector Management is understood as an administrative structure and process of government decisions, as a professional exercise and as an academic discipline; This is what Aguilar Villanueva [1] points out, which focuses on two trends, the public and the managerial; the first of public reactivation to the PA and the second, which emphasizes the reconstruction of the administrative capacity of the PA, which is directly related to the adjustment measures and tax balance.

This is how they have emerged with the purpose of neutralizing the fiscal and administrative malformations of the governments (authoritarian or not) of the social states of the past, offering governmental responses to the social and economic transformations that contemporary societies are experiencing and leaving behind the criticisms that on various fronts they question the obsolescence of the accepted theory of the PA and its faulty practices.

Governance is the process by which the actors of a society decide their coexistence objectives —fundamental and conjunctural— and the ways of coordinating to achieve them: their sense of direction and their ability to lead.

This concept includes the distinction between managerial capacity and managerial effectiveness of government. It is not taken for granted that managerial effectiveness follows from having endowed a government with the institutional, fiscal, analytical and administrative capacities to direct that are considered necessary or sufficient in the pursuit of achieving certain results.

Contributions of the OD to the AP, Pardo [19]

New organizational values: this implies a change in the ways of assuming the public function beyond technical aspects. We can include here values such as honesty, service vocation, taste for work, companionship, new ways of solving personal differences that influence work performance or the aspect of ethics.

Better performance: refers to technical aspects that complement the previous point, among which the administrative functions of planning, organization, division of labor, decision-making, control, use of resources in a rational and transparent way stand out.

Organizational Climate: A positive change in the organizational climate includes the use of conflict resolution techniques to improve human relationships. This point is of particular importance, since even customer service can be affected by changes in the organizational climate.

Efficiency: it is about meeting objectives, internal and external. The change in the organization motivated by the intervention of organizational development, must be an element that turns an inefficient organization into an agile, flexible organization capable of meeting the objectives and expectations that are head of it.

Culture and Organizational Change

In every organization there are patterns of behavior and organizational culture, such as "behavioral manners and the underlying beliefs, values, norms and premises" Cusma Saldaña [12] that goes beyond organizational performance or formal organization: there are also vices and customs that do not they can always be socially correct.

In each organization there is its own culture and therefore behavioral factors. In the case of municipal public administrations, we can add that as long as they only work to meet legal or administrative requirements, they act more for factional interests or there is no continuity in the programs that are applied, the techniques of organizational change will go directly to failure.

The organizational structure and its components

All planned organizational change, objective of Organizational Development, part of an existing reality: The first configuration of an organization is defined by its structure.

Through this topic we will review relevant information on "Organizational Structure".

Definition of organizational structure

The organizational structure, it is more than an organization chart, it is an interweaving that guides the horizontal or vertical relationships that occur between the positions of the organization to develop the tasks with which it seeks to achieve the organizational objectives.

Defines how job duties are formally divided, grouped, and coordinated.

Elements that define the organizational structure

There are six commonly known elements that define the Organizational Structure.

- Job specialization
- Departmentalization
- Chain of command
- Control section
- Centralization and decentralization
- Formalization

Organizational designs

Considering that the elements that are presented in the definition of the organizational structure have diverse variations and intensities, organizations adopt different routes for their design.

Simple structure

Simple structure is one that has a low degree of departmentalization, wide sections of control, centralization of authority in a single person and a low degree of formalization.

Bureaucracy

Bureaucracy, in the most technical-scientific sense of the concept, of the ideal type proposed by the German sociologist Max Weber, is characterized by an operation of highly routine activities, which functions with a high level of specialization; formalized policies and rules; interlocking authority, narrow span of control, and decision-making that respects the chain of command; all grouped in a functional way.

Matrix or matrix structure

Matrix structure or matrix is one that combines two forms of departmentalization (functional and product) creating dual lines of authority. This breaks the concept of unity of command, since the employees working under this structure have two bosses.

Team structure

Team structure is based on the use of teams to coordinate the activities of the organization. This structure breaks with the departmental grouping and decentralizes decision-making to a work team level, for which the staff must be generalists and specialists.

Virtual design

Virtual design is one that outsources most of its business functions, is highly centralized and with little or no departmentalization.

Borderless design

Borderless Design seeks to eliminate the chain of command, has unlimited span of control, and replaces departments with empowered teams. To achieve continuous growth, large organizations have used this

The situation of some municipal public administrations in Mexico is difficult and complex, and they face many adversities. According to Enrique Cabrero in his essay Towards the construction of an agenda for municipal administrative reform in Mexico, the following problematic situations stand out [6]:

62% of Mexican municipalities present an institutional capacity index with a value lower than 6 points (on a scale of 10), with only 4 municipalities with a score higher than 9.

The index measures:

- Operating efficiency
- Income generation
- Service coverage
- Training
- The planning instruments
- The regulation

45% of the municipalities nationwide do not carry out project evaluation actions.

54% do not have some kind of inventory and material resource management system.

74% of the municipalities do not have written development plans.

63% of the municipalities do not have a basic internal administrative regulation, that is, they explicitly indicate how procedures, programs, planning and the use of resources should be carried out, which generates disorder, corruption and inefficiency.

74% of the country's municipalities do not have a planning regulation, which generates improvisation, corruption, uncertainty and few orderly and coherent government actions, as well as non-compliance with objectives.

80% of the municipalities do not have a legal element that regulates, organizes and orders the actions in terms of time, resources and objectives.

61% of the municipalities do not have a Senior Official's Office or equivalent area.

B. Federal Order and Efficient Management

In the federal government managed by the president of Mexico Andrés Manuel López Obrador, measures have been presented focused, in his own words, to "put order and make transparent the public resources that are delivered to the beneficiaries", Forbes [13] this on the extinction of trusts, another of the measures was the disappearance of support for childcare centers so that the resource was delivered directly to the families of the minors Antúnez Estrada [2],

measures taken on a so-called austerity policy, without entering into discussion about the relevance or not of These measures, this generated that a large number of people turned to see what is being done in the government in relation to public finances, considering that the State has the function of contributing to the creation of national wealth.

The application of austerity measures has a history of 40 years in our country, since the late 1980s in the opinion of Moreno-Brid et al. [17], which point out the effects that cuts in public spending have had on investment and economic growth in Mexico, which have been adverse and have impacted on the country's economic growth rate.

In relation to public finances, Serra Rojas [21] establishes that these "constitute a discipline that studies the activities of the State that are aimed at creating the institutions, methods and principles necessary for the economic development of a nation." For its part, for Araneda Dörr [3] the "State constitutes a legal person endowed with will, responsible for obtaining certain ends for the collective benefit".

In accordance with the previous definitions, the State must carry out its financial activity seeking to achieve its own purposes, in line with what the CPEUM itself says, in its article 26, which literally states:

The State will organize a democratic planning system for national development that gives solidity, dynamism, competitiveness, permanence and equity to the growth of the economy for the independence and political, social and cultural democratization of the nation.

It is possible to establish the obligation of the State through public finances to determine the way in which it should participate to promote economic growth, without forgetting the important participation that private initiative must have, for which, the State must generate the conditions stability of macroeconomic variables and promote equal opportunities schemes for the development of human capital that promote productive activities and regulate the functioning of markets Chávez Presa & Budebo, [9].

While the activities that make up public finances, these are studied in the so-called Financial Law, defined by Serra Rojas [21], as "the branch of public law that deals with public finances, that is, it refers to the income and expenses of the State" in general terms, it manages the economic resources to satisfy social needs. In order for the State to comply with its constitutional obligations, it is necessary to have the resources which come mainly from the collection of the wealth of the governed, always under the applicable legal regulations, from the administration of their patrimony and from the expenditure of the necessary expenses for meet the needs of society, which as a whole is called the financial activity of the State, which in turn is part of public finances and is made up of the income and expenses of the State, for which it is important to have the Law of Income and Expenditure Budget of the Federation.

These public finances are the main column of Mexican federalism and involve the issuance of paper money and regulation of banking and stock market activity, which derives from the internal economic process and the exchange with the exterior, Guevara Baltazar et al. [14].

The classic idea of public finances that was maintained since the French Revolution limited the aims of the State and reduced its means of action, its assets. A restricted purpose naturally corresponded scarce resources, Araneda Dörr [3]

Making a small historical review of public finances, we can identify that they take the approach of each theory that emerged in the classical and neoclassical times, so we have: Rodríguez Sánchez [20]

Classic Period

1. **The sociological school of finance:** It maintains that the elite of society takes over the state government and exploits it for their own benefit.
2. **Sociological and political theory:** It stipulates that the growth of the State in contemporary societies was due to the restructuring of the economy and society, a product of industrial and urban development that generates a growing demand for public goods and services that is solved through public spending.
3. **Financial theory:** For Benvenuto Griziotti, the decision of the State that determines its expenses is prior to the choice of resources and independent of these; the purposes of the State are limited, which also restricts the total amount of public expenditures compared to a relative abundance of resources to which it can turn; and the power that it can exercise over individuals excludes the bargaining that characterizes the market economy.

Neoclassical Period

Rodríguez Sánchez [20] explains that within this period there are two important currents, the Anglo-Saxon with Alfred Marshall and Arthur Cecil and the Scandinavian-Italian with Knut Wicksell, Lindhal and Pareto.

1. **Anglo-Saxon theory:** Public finances are reduced to the issues related to the distortion of prices generated by taxes in a competitive economy of partial equilibrium
2. **Scandinavian-Italian theory:** Values the parliamentary approval of the spending budget and understands the just distribution of wealth.

To achieve a greater understanding of the research topic, it is important to define some of the most important concepts, so for the purposes of this research it is understood by:

Austerity: Drastic Fiscal Consolidation Program Aimed at Reducing Fiscal Deficits

Fiscal consolidation: reducing deficits through spending cuts or increases in government revenue

Financial law: The branch of public law that deals with public finances.

Public expenditure: it is the amount of financial, material and human resources that the public sector represented by the government uses for the fulfillment of its functions, among which are primarily that of satisfying the public services of society.

Public income: all those money inflows that the State receives and that allow it to finance the satisfaction of collective needs, that is, that allow it to finance public spending and fulfill its function within society.

Expenditure budget: It is the act by which the expenditure projects of the different administrative units of the State are foreseen and authorized for a fiscal year. Contains a set of mandatory compliance rules, to have financial resources.
Income budget: all items that allow the State to raise resources, such as taxes, fees and duties are considered.

Some factors that slow down the success of PM according to CusmaSaldaña [12] are the following:

- Low performance of the State, which generates distrust and citizen dissatisfaction.
- Weak intergovernmental and intersect oral articulation.
- Inadequate design of the organizational structure of functions.
- Difficulties in making good plans that fit in with your budget.
- Lack of information and knowledge management systems and methods.
- Inadequate human resource policy and management.
- Lacks in infrastructure, equipment and logistics of the entities.
- Lack of monitoring and evaluation of the expected results and impacts.
- Inefficiencies in production processes.
- Outside of obtaining results for the citizen.

IV. DISCUSSION AND PROPOSALS FOR SOLUTION

Proposals for the approach of Public Organizational Development (POD) as a Public Management tool with a focus mainly on the Municipal scope

According to Vargas Hernández [22] what has been analyzed, it is recommended that management activities be linked and focused mainly on the needs and rights of citizens.

Redesign

Finally, it should be said that when the elements, designs and factors that determine the organizational structure have weakening features, they are calling the entity to a Redesign of the Organizational Structure, based mainly on three main operations:

Behavior of the actors

In a redesign, the behavior of the actors plays a fundamental role, to maximize their performance and satisfaction, individual differences, experience, personality and the nature of their activities must be taken into account.

Actions to take

When proposing the redesign of the organizational structure, the following must be done:

1. Analyze the orientation of each employee to be placed in the appropriate position.
2. "Know how" and in what activities each person works best.

Analysis of the Aspects to consider

The redesign of the organizational structure focused on changing the implicit model of the POD, where each person has a different perception regarding their variables and interactions.

Faced with the great challenges involved in serving citizens, the operational structure of local governments has traditionally been “neglected”.

The definition of the organizational structure is central for the proper operation of the government to achieve the desired results. It is therefore pertinent that the subject be treated with the care it deserves, beyond the unfortunate habit of “placing” people in positions.

From the exercise of designing the organization according to the needs of the execution of the plans through the programs, there will be the foundations for the success of the exercise of government.

The contempt for this momentous task will be reflected in the limited scope of the results.

1. **Operations** - Maximize the potential of existing operations Optimize management capacity and develop continuous improvement of productivity and cost structure and take advantage of growth opportunities.
2. **Projects in development and advanced projects** - Grant growth through projects in development Develop, build and put into operation the projects that meet the strict criteria of content and costs.
3. **Production** - Extend the growth portfolio Invest continuously through the management cycle to ensure a growing project portfolio at all stages.
4. **Sustainable Development** - Develop and improve the sustainability of operations Prioritize health and safety, care for the environment, the well-being of our communities, best governance practices and a culture of service based on ethics and social responsibility.

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